

Gingivitis : A Litmus Test For Oral Health

Brijendra Singh¹
Mohammad Aamir²
Rainna Agarwal³
Khushboo⁴
Zeba Ambreen⁵
Akanksha Kashyap⁶

Associate Professor¹
 Department of Periodontology
 BBDCODS, BBDU
 Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh
 Assistant Professor²
 Department of Periodontology
 BBDCODS, BBDU
 Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh
 Junior Resident³
 Department of Periodontology
 BBDCODS, BBDU
 Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh
 Assistant Professor⁴
 Dept. of Public Health Dentistry
 K.G.D.U.
 Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh
 Junior Resident⁵
 Dept. of Pediatric & Preventive Dentistry
 Dr. Ziauddin Ahmad Dental College
 Aligarh Muslim University,
 Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh
 Associate Professor⁶
 Department of Periodontology
 BBDCODS, BBDU
 Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh

Abstract

Gingivitis is inflammation of the gingiva caused by plaque buildup and can be treated by improving oral hygiene. Most adults are affected at some point in their lives. Symptoms can get worse if the root cause is not addressed the accumulation of bacteria around the teeth is the most common cause of gingivitis. The main symptoms of gingivitis are red, swollen gums and bleeding when you brush your teeth. Gingivitis can often be cured with good oral hygiene. Brushing longer and more often, flossing regularly, and using an antiseptic mouthwash can help.

Introduction

We can define gingivitis as an inflammatory disease of the gingival tissue, most commonly caused by bacterial infection. It differs from periodontitis in that there is no loss of attachment and therefore no movement of the junctional epithelium. This condition is confined to soft tissue areas of the gingival epithelium and connective tissue^[1]. Of all periodontal diseases, gingivitis is considered the most common. There are different forms of gingivitis, depending on clinical presentation, duration of infection, severity and etiology. However, the most common variant is the chronic form of gingivitis caused by dental plaque. Clinically, gingival tissue is characterized by swelling, redness, tenderness, a shiny surface, and bleeding on careful examination. Because gingivitis rarely causes spontaneous bleeding and is generally painless, many patients are unaware of the disease and seek help^[2]

Etiology

Gingivitis is caused by the buildup of microbial plaque on or near the ridges of the gums. Microorganisms more closely associated with the etiology of gingivitis

include Streptococcus, Fusobacterium, Actinomycetes, Veillonella, and Treponema species. Bacteroides, Capnocytophaga, and Eikenella may also be involved in the etiology of this disease. There may be other local or systemic etiologies that increase tissue susceptibility to plaque deposition and microbial attack^[3]. Based on etiology, gingivitis can be classified into different types.

Plaque Induced Gingivitis

Plaque is a thin film that forms on the surface of teeth due to poor oral hygiene. If not removed regularly, it can harden and form tartar. Plaque harbors a large number of bacteria, which can lead to inflammation of the gum tissue.

Several factors such as crowded teeth, poorly aligned teeth, ongoing orthodontic treatment and the presence of dentures make it difficult to maintain plaque control. rash gingivitis.

In children, tooth eruption is often associated with gingivitis. This is because plaque buildup tends to increase in areas where primary teeth have come off, and maintaining oral hygiene in these areas can be difficult, so permanent teeth can erupt.

Access this article online

Website:

 www.updent.in

Quick Response Code:

Diet Related Gingivitis

This can be caused by a lack of vitamin C. A modern lifestyle with increased intake of refined carbohydrates and a high ratio of omega-6 to omega-3 fatty acids accelerates the inflammatory process. We know that it is possible^[4]. The mechanism by which high-glycemic-index carbohydrates promote inflammatory processes is based on NFkB activation and oxidative stress^{[5][6]}.

Hormonal Gingivitis

During pregnancy, not only do hormone levels change, but blood vessels also tend to dilate. These factors cause an increased inflammatory response in the gingival tissue, even if only a small amount of plaque builds up. Indeed, it has been suggested that estrogen levels determine the severity of gingivitis that develops against gingival biofilms^{[7][8]}.

During puberty, hormonal changes in gingival tissue respond to plaque accumulation under the influence of estrogen and testosterone. Receptors for estrogen are specifically present in the basal and spinous layers of the epithelium. In connective tissue, such receptors are found on small vessel fibroblasts and endothelial cells. Therefore, the gingiva is a likely target organ for these steroid hormones, causing gingivitis. Adolescent gingivitis has been observed to develop earlier in girls (ages 11–13) than in boys (ages 13–14)^[9].

Drug Induced Gingivitis

Various drugs used for systemic diseases can cause gingivitis as a side effect. Phenytoin (used for epileptic seizures), calcium channel blockers (used for angina pectoris, hypertension), anticoagulants and fibrinolytics, oral contraceptives, protease inhibitors, and vitamin A. The mechanism behind this gingivitis is believed to be the ability of these drug metabolites to induce fibroblast proliferation. When the balance between extracellular matrix synthesis and degradation is disrupted, immature proteins accumulate in the extracellular matrix, especially collagen. This leads to gingivitis^[10].

Various risk and influence factors, in addition to those already mentioned, can contribute to the development of gingivitis. These include smoking or chewing tobacco, systemic disease, genetic factors (hereditary gingival fibromatosis), and local disease (dry mouth, crowded teeth).

Epidemiology

Gingivitis is more common in men than women, as women have been found to follow better oral care regimens. It is common in both children and adults. Studies have shown that gingivitis is more common in people of lower socioeconomic status. People of higher socioeconomic status tend to have more positive attitudes toward maintaining oral health. They also have better access to health care options. Studies show that gingivitis is more common in pregnant women than in non-pregnant women. Additionally, a more severe form of gingivitis has been observed more frequently in pregnant women^[11].

The most commonly observed types of gingivitis are plaque-induced, hormonal, acute ulcerative necrosis, drug-induced, or spontaneous hyperplastic gingivitis. Basically, the main form of gingivitis is plaque-induced. In fact, this type accounts for far more cases than all other variants combined^[12].

Pathophysiology

As per Page and Schroeder periodontal disease can be distinguished in multiple stages^[13]. Pathophysiologically, gingivitis is divided into early, early, and established stages, and periodontitis is called advanced stage.

Initial Lesion

This stage is characterized by an acute exudative inflammatory response, increased gingival fluid flow, and migration of neutrophils from the subgingival plexus vessels located in the gingival connective tissue to the gingival sulcus. Changes in the connective tissue matrix near blood vessels lead to fibrin accumulation in this area. Early lesions are seen within 4 days of the onset of plaque accumulation. There is collagen breakdown caused by collagenase and other enzymes secreted by neutrophils. At this stage, about 5% to 10% of the connective tissue is occupied by inflammatory infiltrates^[12].

Early Lesions

Early lesions are consistent with late-onset hypersensitivity. Usually he occurs a week after plaque begins to build up. At this stage, clinical symptoms of gingivitis, such as redness and bleeding of the gums, begin to appear. The major inflammatory cells in this lesion are lymphocytes and macrophages, accounting for 75% of the total. few plasma cells are also seen. Inflammatory

infiltrates occupying 5% to 15% of the connective tissue of the gingival line, along with a 60% to 70% reduction in collagen in the affected areas. In addition, local fibroblasts undergo a number of pathological changes, resulting in an ever-increasing number of gingival fluidflow and migrating leukocytes into the area. Neutrophils and mononuclear cells also increase in the junctional epithelium.early lesions may stay longer than expected^[12].

Established Lesion

In this stage, the amount of macrophages, plasma cells, T-lymphocytes and B-lymphocytes increases, along with increased collagenolytic activity. At this stage, small periodontal pockets lined with pocket epithelium are formed. Lesions show a high degree of organization. Severity of gingivitis has been suggested to be correlated with increased numbers of B and plasma cells and decreased numbers of T cells. Established lesions can follow two pathways. Alternatively, it progresses to more destructive lesions, likely related to altered microbial flora or gum infection. This stage has been shown to be reversible after effective periodontal treatment, leading to increased microbial populations associated with periodontal health. This directly correlates with plasma cell and lymphocyte depletion^[12].

Advanced Disease

This stage is the transition to periodontitis. The clinical loss of attachment seen in this case is difficult to repair. Inflammatory changes and bacterial infections begin to affect the tooth's supporting tissues and surrounding structures such as the gingiva, periodontal ligament and alveolar bone, leading to their destruction and ultimately tooth loss^{[14],[15]}.

Physical Features of Gingivitis

Healthy gingival tissue in black patients appears pink or pigmented, firm, and non-bleeding with no signs of redness or swelling after gently passing the periodontal probe along the gingival crevice. On periodontal probing, healthy gum fissures are less than 3 mm and no bone loss is seen on radiographs. In many cases, gingivitis may be present and progress without symptoms, so patients may not be aware of it. When symptomatic, patients usually report bleeding gums when brushing, flossing, and sometimes eating

particularly hard foods, and bad breath that persists despite oral hygiene. , reveals the presence of inflamed, tender gums, usually bleeding on careful examination. The gingival margin, which presents a razor-sharp appearance, and the punctate appearance of gingival tissue found in healthy gums are replaced by a more rounded and glossy appearance. Considerable plaque and tartar deposits are usually seen. In chronic gingivitis, edema or hyperplasia may increase the size of the gingival tissue at the incisal, resulting in probe depths greater than 3 mm. However, no attachment loss occurred. These are called falsepockets.

The gingival swelling can be graded into four types.

- Grade 0: No signs of gingival swelling.
- Grade I: Swelling that is confined to the interdental papilla region.
- Grade II: Swelling involving both the interdental papilla and the marginal gingiva.
- Grade III: Swelling that covers three-fourths or more of the crown structure.

The Gingival Index (GI)

The purpose of the gingival index is to indicate the quality of the gingival tissue, differentiating the severity of the lesion, and the location of the alteration concerning the four areas that form the perimeter of the marginal gingiva. The criteria included in the index are only related to qualitative changes in the gingiva. A score from 0 to 3 is given to each area of the tooth (mesial, distal, vestibular, palatine, or lingual), this is the GI for the area. The GI score per tooth is achieved by adding the scores from the four areas and then dividing this number by four. The GI for the subject is obtained by adding the indices of each tooth and dividing them into the number of teeth that were examined^[16].

Criteria For Gingival Index System

- 0: Normal gingiva
- 1: Mild inflammation – a slight color change, slight edema. No bleeding on probing.
- 2: Moderate inflammation – redness, edema, and glazing. Bleeding on probing.
- 3: Severe inflammation – marked redness and edema. Ulceration. Tendency to spontaneous bleeding^[16].

Classification of Gingivitis

In the latest International Workshop for a Classification of Periodontal Diseases and Conditions in 2017, gingival diseases have been classified as follow:

Gingivitis - dental biofilm-induced

1. Associated with dental biofilm alone
2. Mediated by systemic or local risk factors
3. Drug-influenced gingival enlargement
- Gingival diseases non-dental biofilm induced
 1. Genetic/ developmental disorders
 2. Specific infections
 3. Inflammatory and immune conditions
 4. Reactive processes
 5. Neoplasms
 6. Endocrine, nutritional, and metabolic diseases
 7. Traumatic lesions
 8. Gingival pigmentation^[17]

Evaluation

Because gingivitis is a soft-tissue disease, it usually does not require a radiographic evaluation. However, in some cases, it can help distinguish between gingivitis and periodontitis. Laboratory tests are usually not required.

Treatment/Administration

The main goal of treating gingivitis is to reduce inflammation. This is accomplished by removing plaque using a variety of instruments^[18]. Early-stage gingivitis can be easily managed once the patient begins to follow an oral hygiene protocol that includes regular brushing using good technique and interdental hygiene such as the use of dental floss and interdental brushes. Plaque and tartar removal is also done professionally through scaling and route planning depending on the severity of the condition.

In the case of drug-induced gum overgrowth, your doctor may change the drug to improve the outcome of the condition. Dietary supplements may be prescribed for malnutrition. Medications in the form of antiseptic mouthwashes containing chlorhexidine can also be prescribed in conjunction with mechanical plaque removal. have been suggested to significantly reduce biofilm accumulation in The concentration of chlorhexidine rinse does not affect its efficacy^[19].

There are studies on the effects of medicinal or herbal plants for treating gingivitis. The mechanism of action of these plants against gingivitis is due to their anti-inflammatory properties. These medicinal plants include

pomegranate, tea and chamomile. The flavonoids and tannins found in these plants are powerful anti-inflammatory and astringent phytochemicals. Therefore, both bleeding and inflammation of the gums can be treated^[20]. Several studies have proven synergistic when herbal botanicals are combined with traditional mechanical plaque removal methods. eg. Scaling^[21].

Differential Diagnosi

Gingivitis can be distinguished from periodontitis by the loss of attachment clinically detectable in the latter during periodontal probing^[22]. It can also be distinguished histologically and radiologically.

Prognosis

Gingivitis, if recognized and treated, is easily resolved because the condition is reversible and the altered tissue returns to normal once the tooth biofilm is removed. As gingivitis progresses to periodontitis, loss of connective tissue and destruction of bone can occur, ultimately leading to tooth loss.

Complications

The most common complication or sequela of chronic gingivitis is the spread of inflammation to underlying tissue and bone, causing periodontitis. The end result of such events is tooth loss.

However, gingivitis does not always progress to periodontal disease. Deterrence and patient education.

Patients should be educated about the importance of good oral hygiene, which can prevent plaque formation and associated gingivitis. Correct brushing techniques should be taught according to individual needs, frequency of brushing and use of interdental hygiene. In addition, the importance of regular visits to the dentist should be emphasized. Finally, the use of mouthwash is also recommended^{[23][24]}.

Improving Healthcare Team Outcomes

Improving gingivitis outcomes requires an interprofessional approach to identify the cause of the disease and to intervene early. In addition, plaque-induced gingivitis can occur at any age in the edentulous population, so thorough knowledge of epidemiological patterns is required to plan public health services. Periodontal disease is not limited to destruction of periodontal tissue

Pre-Scaling & Root Planing

Post-Scaling & Root Planing

References

1. Sonika S, Esther Nalini H, Arun Kumar Prasad P, Renuka Devi R. Evaluation Of Salivary Nlrp3 (nucleotide Oligomerisation Domain-like Receptor-3) Inflammasome- Related Protein In Periodontal Health And Periodontitis With And Without Type Ii Diabetes Mellitus—a Cross Sectional Study. *International Journal of ClinicalDentistry*. 2022 Jul 1;15(3).
2. Trombelli L, Farina R, Silva CO, Tatakis DN. Plaque-induced gingivitis: Case definition and diagnostic considerations. *Journal of clinical periodontology*. 2018 Jun;45:S44-67. Bosma-den Boer MM, van Wetten ML, Pruimboom L. Chronic inflammatory diseases are stimulated by current lifestyle: how diet, stress levels and medication prevent our body from recovering. *Nutr Metab (Lond)*. 2012 Apr 17;9(1):32.
3. Trombelli L, Farina R, Silva CO, Tatakis DN. Plaque-induced gingivitis: Case definition and diagnostic considerations. *Journal of clinical periodontology*. 2018 Jun;45:S44-67.
4. Bosma-den Boer MM, van Wetten ML, Pruimboom L. Chronic inflammatory diseases are stimulated by current lifestyle: how diet, stress levels and medication prevent our body from recovering. *Nutrition & metabolism*. 2012 Dec;9(1):1-4.
5. Dickinson S, Hancock DP, Petocz P, Ceriello A, Brand-Miller J. High-glycemic index carbohydrate increases nuclear factor- κ B activation in mononuclear cells of young, lean healthy subjects. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*. 2008 May 1;87(5):1188-93.
6. Hu Y, Block G, Norkus EP, Morrow JD, Dietrich M, Hudes M. Relations of glycemic index and glycemic load with plasma oxidative stress markers. *The American journal of clinical nutrition*. 2006 Jun 1;84(1):70-6.
7. Gürsoy M, Gürsoy UK, Sorsa T, Pajukanta R, Könönen E. High salivary estrogen and risk of developing pregnancy gingivitis. *J Periodontol*. 2013 Sep;84(9):1281-9.
8. Bilinska M, Sokalski J. Pregnancy gingivitis and tumor gravidarum. *Ginekologia Polska*. 2016;87(4):310-3.
9. Nakagawa S, Fujii H, Machida Y, Okuda K. A longitudinal study from prepuberty to puberty of gingivitis: correlation between the occurrence of Prevotella intermedia and sex hormones. *Journal of clinical periodontology*. 1994 Nov;21(10):658-65.
10. Tungare S, Paranjpe AG. Drug induced gingival overgrowth. In *StatPearls Publishing* [Internet]. 2021 Sep 25. StatPearls Publishing.
11. Kashetty M, Kumbhar S, Patil S, Patil P. Oral hygiene status, gingival status, periodontal status, and treatment needs among pregnant and nonpregnant women: A comparative study. *Journal of Indian Society of Periodontology*. 2018 Mar 1;22(2):164-70.
12. Page RC. Gingivitis. *J Clin Periodontol*. 1986 May;13(5):345-59.
13. Page RC, Schroeder HE. Pathogenesis of inflammatory periodontal disease. A summary of current work. *Lab Invest*. 1976 Mar;34(3):235-49.
14. Bosshardt DD, Selvig KA. Dental cementum: the dynamic tissue covering of the root. *Periodontol 2000*. 1997 Feb;13:41-75.
15. Syndergaard B, Al-Sabbagh M, Kryscio RJ, Xi J, Ding X, Ebersole JL, Miller CS. Salivary biomarkers associated with gingivitis and response to therapy. *J Periodontol*. 2014 Aug;85(8):e295-303.
16. Loe H. The Gingival Index, the Plaque Index and the Retention Index Systems. *J Periodontol*. 1967 Nov-Dec;38(6):
17. Caton JG, Armitage G, Berglundh T, Chapple IL, Jepsen S, Kornman KS, Mealey BL, Papananou PN, Sanz M, Tonetti MS. A new classification scheme for periodontal and peri-implant diseases and conditions—Introduction and key changes from the 1999 classification. *Journal of periodontology*. 2018 Jun;89:S1-8.
18. Pozo P, Valenzuela MA, Melej C, Zaldivar M, Puente J, Martinez B, Gamonal J. Longitudinal analysis of metalloproteinases, tissue inhibitors of metalloproteinases and clinical parameters in gingival crevicular fluid from periodontitis-affected patients. *Journal of periodontal research*. 2005 Jun;40(3):199-207.
19. James P, Worthington HV, Parnell C, Harding M, Lamont T, Cheung A, Whelton H, Riley P. Chlorhexidine mouthrinse as an adjunctive treatment for gingival health. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2017(3).
20. Safiaghdam H, Oveissi V, Bahramsoltani R, Farzaei MH, Rahimi R. Medicinal plants for gingivitis: a review of clinical trials. *Iranian journal of basic medical sciences*. 2018 Oct;21(10):978.
21. Ajmera N, Chatterjee A, Goyal V. Aloe vera: Its effect on gingivitis. *Journal of Indian Society of Periodontology*. 2013 Jul;17(4):435.
22. Dietrich T, Kaye EK, Nunn ME, Van Dyke T, Garcia RI. Gingivitis susceptibility and its relation to periodontitis in men. *Journal of dental research*. 2006 Dec;85(12):1134-7.
23. Woelber JP, Bremer K, Vach K, König D, Hellwig E, Ratka-Krüger P, Al-Ahmad A, Tennert CJ. An oral health optimized diet can reduce gingival and periodontal inflammation in humans—a randomized controlled pilot study. *BMC oral health*. 2017 Dec;17(1):1-8.
24. Díaz Sánchez RM, Castillo-Dalí G, Fernández-Olavarria A, Mosquera-Pérez R, Delgado-Muñoz JM, Gutiérrez-Pérez JL, Torres-Lagares D. A Prospective, Double-Blind, Randomized, Controlled Clinical Trial in the Gingivitis Prevention with an Oligomeric Proanthocyanidin Nutritional Supplement. *Mediators Inflamm*. 2017;2017:7460780.
25. Sánchez RD, Castillo-Dalí G, Fernández-Olavarria A, Mosquera-Pérez R, Delgado-Muñoz JM, Gutiérrez-Pérez JL, Torres-Lagares D. A prospective, double-blind, randomized, controlled clinical trial in the gingivitis prevention with an oligomeric proanthocyanidin nutritional supplement. *Mediators of Inflammation*. 2017;2017.
26. Dhadse P, Gattani D, Mishra R. The link between periodontal disease and cardiovascular disease: How far we have come in last two decades. *Journal of Indian Society of Periodontology*. 2010 Jul;14(3):148.
27. Haerian-Ardakani A, Eslami Z, Rashidi-Meibodi F, Haerian A, Dallalnejad P, Shekari M, Taghavi AM, Akbari S. Relationship between maternal periodontal disease and low birth weight babies. *Iranian journal of reproductive medicine*. 2013 Aug;11(8):625.